

ELECTRICAL AND ELECTRONICS ENGINEERING

FEASIBILITY STUDY OF ELEVATOR AND SHORT CIRCUIT CALCULATIONS FOR A RESIDENTIAL COMPLEX

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Abstract

This paper presents a feasibility study for calculating elevator equipment and short-circuit currents in electrical networks of a residential complex. Key aspects of elevator operation are considered, including an assessment of the time spent on acceleration, braking, and door operation, as well as the calculation of annual electricity consumption. An analysis of electrical network parameters is carried out, including the determination of active and reactive resistances of cable lines, transformers, and circuit breakers. Calculations of short-circuit currents at critical points in the network are performed to ensure the reliability and safety of power supply.

Particular attention is paid to the development of an elevator monitoring system based on an automated dispatch control system (ADCS). The system provides for monitoring of elevator operation, voice communication with the dispatcher, as well as the functions of transporting fire brigades. The calculation results confirm the compliance of the proposed solutions with modern requirements for energy efficiency, safety, and reliability. Key results and recommendations are aimed at improving the comfort of residents, reducing operating costs, and ensuring the smooth operation of the electrical infrastructure of the residential complex.

Keywords : Economy, elevator equipment, residential complex, elevator energy consumption, elevator monitoring system, ASUD (automated control system for dispatching), electrical network safety, specific energy consumption, energy efficiency of a residential complex

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I . INTRODUCTION

The feasibility study of elevator calculations and short circuits in a residential complex is a key design element that determines the efficiency of the operation of lifting mechanisms and the safety of electrical equipment. It is important to consider various factors that affect the operational characteristics of elevators, including load capacity, speed, operating modes and the number of stops. One of the main aspects of the feasibility study is the economic efficiency of the proposed

solutions. It is necessary to calculate the costs of installing and servicing elevators, as well as the cost of possible damage from short circuits. Such calculations will help to select the optimal technologies and equipment that not only meet safety requirements, but also ensure the minimization of operating costs in the long term.

Based on the data provided, a summary of the building's characteristics was formed:

TABLE 1. TECHNICAL AND ECONOMIC INDICATORS

Nºp/p	Name of indicators	Quantity	Units of measurement
1	Building area	685,0	m ²
2	Number of floors	17	Floor
3	Number of floors incl.	19	Floor
	-above mark 0.000	18	
	-below mark 0.000	1	
4	Number of sections	1	Section
5	Building volume incl.	36921,68	m ²
	-above mark 0.000	35118,08	
	-below mark 0.000	1803,6	
6	Total area of the residential building	10171,96	m ²
7	Living area of the apartment	3452,4	m ²
8	Total area of apartments (excluding balconies and loggias)	6619,8	m ²
9	Total area of apartments (including balconies and loggias)	6913,9	m ²
10	Number of apartments (total)	106	Piece
11	One-room apartments	35	Piece
12	Two-room apartments	28	Piece
13	Three-room apartments	32	Piece
14	Four-room apartments	11	Piece
15	Area of common areas	2451,4	m ²

Calculation of the number of elevators according to the methodology of SP 31-107-2004,

Initial data for calculation:

1. Number of floors (N) - 17

2. Purpose of the 1st floor: 0 — residential.

3. Floor height (H_{1эт} и H_{1тэт}):

- height of the first floor H_{1,fl} = 3.2 m

- height of the remaining floors H_{t,fl} = 3.2 m

4. occupancy of one floor of a section, (a_i) 19 per.

5. purpose of the building: 1 - residential or dormitory for workers, 2 - dormitory for students

6. 5-minute flow intensity indicator

Uphill (i_p): 4.95 %

Downhill (i_c): 2.55 %

7. Elevator movement interval (t_i): 100 seconds (comfort level - satisfactory). <=60s - excellent, <=80s - good, <=100s - satisfactory

8. Pre-accepted elevator speed (V): 1.0 m/s.

1.0, 1.6, 2.5, 4.0 m/s

Calculation:

1) To calculate the number of floors with population using the elevator, the following formulas are used:

$$N_{ip} = N - 4$$

Where:

N — total number of floors;

4 — floors that are not counted for upward movement (e.g. technical floors or basement floors).

We substitute the values:

$$N_{ip} = 17 - 4 = 13$$

For passengers going down (N_{is}):

$$N_{is} = N - 5$$

Where: 5 — floors excluded from downward movement.

Substitute the values:

$$N_{is} = 17 - 5 = 12$$

2) The value of the calculated equivalent peak passenger flow, rising up from the main boarding floor A_{ip} and descending to the main boarding floor A_{ic}, according to formulas (1) and (2):

The given formulas for calculating the value of the peak

passenger flow, going up (A_{ip}), and going down (A_{is}), to the main boarding floor may look like this:

$$A_{ip} = \sum_{j=1}^n K_{ij} \cdot P_j \quad (1)$$

Where:

K_{ij} - coefficient taking into account the distribution of passengers traveling upwards from floor i to floor j,

P_j - passenger flow intensity on floor j,

n - total number of floors.

A_{is} – exactly the same:

$$A_{is} = \sum_{j=1}^n K_{ji} \cdot P_j \quad (2)$$

Where:

K_{ji} - coefficient taking into account the distribution of passengers going down, from floor j to floor i,

• K_{ji} and K_{ij} depend on the characteristics of the building (e.g. number of floors, purpose of floors) and the distribution of passenger flows.

• Formulas can be adapted depending on additional conditions (e.g. peak load times, equipment capacity limitations).

The formula for calculating the value of the estimated equivalent peak passenger flow rising upward (A_{ip}) is as follows:

$$A_{ip} = 0.12 \cdot i_p \cdot a_i \cdot N_{ip}$$

A_{ip} - Estimated peak passenger flow moving upward from the main landing floor (pers/min),

i_p - intensity of passenger flow in the building (pers/hour),

a_i - the proportion of passengers going up from the main boarding floor (in fractions of one),

N_{ip} - total number of floors served by passengers going up.

Knowing all the values we can determine:

$$A_{ip} = 0.12 \cdot i_p \cdot a_i \cdot N_{ip} = 0.12 \cdot 4.95 \cdot 19 \cdot 13 = 146.7$$

$$\approx 147 \text{ pers/hour}$$

According to the given formula:

$$A_{ic} = 0.12 \cdot i_c \cdot a_i \cdot N_{ic}$$

Where:

$i_c = 2.55$ — intensity of downward passenger flow (persons/hour);
 $a_i = 19$ — the proportion of passengers heading down from the main boarding floor;
 $N_{ic} = 12$ — number of floors served by passengers heading down.

Substitute the values:

$$A_{ic} = 0.12 \cdot i_c \cdot a_i \cdot N_{ic} = 0.12 \cdot 2.55 \cdot 19 \cdot 12 = 69.912 \approx 70 \text{ pers/hour}$$

To calculate the filling of the cabin of one elevator during ascent (E_p) and descent (E_s), we use the following formulas:

1. Filling the cabin when lifting (E_p):

$$E_p = \frac{A_{ip} \cdot t_i}{3600} = \frac{147 \cdot 100}{3600} = \frac{14700}{3600} = 4.08 \approx 4 \text{ pers}$$

2. Filling the cabin during descent (E_c):

$$E_c = \frac{A_{ic} \cdot t_i}{3600} = \frac{70 \cdot 100}{3600} = \frac{7000}{3600} = 1.94 \approx 2 \text{ pers}$$

where:

- t_i — interval of departure of one elevator (in seconds),
- 3600 — number of seconds in one hour (conversion to hours).

The capacity of the elevator cabin E must be greater than or equal to the occupancy of the elevator cabin on the main landing floor $E \geq E_p$.

TABLE 2. RATIO OF PROBABLE NUMBER OF STOPS ABOVE THE MAIN LANDING FLOOR TO THE NUMBER OF FLOORS WITH POPULATION USING THE ELEVATOR

$\frac{N_{bn}}{N_{ip}}$	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0
k_i	0.6	0.65	0.7	0.75	0.8	0.85	0.9	0.95	1.0	1.05

According to table 2, for the value 0.28, the coefficient $k_i = 0.7$.

Maximum floor level of the top floor (H_{max}):

$$H_{max} = H_{1fl} + (N - 2) \cdot H_{t.fl}$$

we substitute:

$$H_{max} = H_{1st} + (N - 2) \cdot H_{tst} = 3.2 + (17 - 2) \cdot 3.2 = 3.2 + 15 \cdot 3.2 = 3.2 + 48 = 51.2 \text{ m}$$

Probable lift height (H_v):

$$H_v = k_i \cdot H_{max}$$

Let's substitute the values:

$$H_v = k_i \cdot H_{max} = 0.7 \cdot 51.2 = 35.84 \text{ m.}$$

Time of entry or exit of one passenger from the elevator:

According to the data, the width of the elevator doorway = 930 mm.

By standard values:

- For doorway width 900–1000 mm:
- Entry or exit time for one passenger: 1.5 seconds.

Time spent on passengers entering and exiting the elevator cabin:

Formula:

$$t_{4-5} = t_4 + t_5 = 2 \cdot dt \cdot (E_p + E_s)$$

where:

$dt = 1.5$ – time for entry and exit of one passenger.

E_p – filling the cabin when lifting.

E_c – Filling the cabin during descent.

If we put the data into the formula, we get:

$$t_{4-5} = t_4 + t_5 = 2 \cdot dt \cdot (E_p + E_c) = 2 \cdot 1.5 \cdot (4.08 + 1.9) = 2 \cdot 1.5 \cdot 5.98 = 17.94 \approx 18 \text{ sec.}$$

Time spent on accelerating the elevator to its nominal speed, braking, starting and opening the doors:

Let's assume that the time costs are:

$$t_{1-3} = t_1 + t_2 + t_3 + t_4 = 12 \text{ sec.}$$

where:

- $t_1 = \frac{v_n}{a_{acc}}$ — acceleration time to nominal speed ($a_{acc} = 0.9 \text{ m/s}^2$),

Data:

1. Estimated cabin occupancy on the main landing floor during ascent (E_p): 4.07 persons.

2. Capacity of the elevator with a lifting capacity of 400 kg: 5 people.

Condition check:

$$E \geq E_p$$

Substitute the values:

$$5 \geq 4.08$$

Number of probable stops per round trip above the main landing floor:

$$N_{vp} = N_{ip} - N_{ip} \cdot \left(\frac{N_{ip} - 1}{N_{ip}} \right)^{E_p} = 13 - 13 \cdot \left(\frac{12}{13} \right)^{4.08} = 13 - 9.378 = 3.6$$

For the descent:

$$N_{vs} = N_{is} - N_{is} \cdot \left(\frac{N_{is} - 1}{N_{is}} \right)^{E_c} = 12 - 12 \cdot \left(\frac{11}{12} \right)^{1.94} = 12 - 11 = 1.86$$

Let's determine the total number of stops:

$$N_v = N_{vp} + N_{vs} = 3.6 + 1.86 = 5.46 \approx 5.5$$

Ratio of N_{vp} to N_{ip} and coefficient k_i :

$$\frac{N_{vp}}{N_{ip}} = \frac{3.6}{13} = 0.276 \approx 0.28$$

- $t_2 = \frac{v_n}{a_{brak}}$ — braking time to complete stop ($a_{brak} = 0.9 \text{ m/s}^2$),

- t_3 — elevator start time (0.5-1.5 s),

- t_4 — time for opening and closing doors (2-5s).

Total time spent on a round trip:

We use the formula:

$$\Sigma T = t_{1-3} \cdot (N_v + 1) + t_{4-5}$$

where:

- $N_v = 5.5$ — total number of probable stops.

Let's substitute the data:

$$\Sigma T = t_{1-3} \cdot (N_v + 1) + t_{4-5} = 12 \cdot (5.5 + 1) + 18 = 78 + 18 = 96 \text{ s}$$

Round trip time:

Let's use the formula for round trip time:

$$T = \frac{(2 \cdot H_v + h \cdot (N_v + 1))}{V} + 1.1 \cdot \Sigma T$$

where:

- $H_v = 35.84 \text{ m}$ — elevator lift height;

- $h = 2 \text{ m}$ — the distance traveled by the elevator during acceleration and braking.

- $V = 1.00 \text{ m/s}$ — elevator speed.

- $\Sigma T = 96 \text{ s}$ — total time costs.

Let's look at the main components of the calculation:

1. **The distance traveled by the elevator during acceleration and braking:**

- Includes both the distance the elevator travels when reaching its rated speed and the distance it travels when braking.

- This value is often taken from standard tables for specific types of elevators.

2. **Time spent on movement:**

The time it takes an elevator to move from one floor to another (or from the starting point to the end point) is calculated using the formula:

$$T_{movement} = \frac{(2 \cdot H_v + h \cdot (N_v + 1))}{V}$$

Here $2 \cdot H_v$ takes into account the ascent and descent of the elevator, and $h \cdot (N_v + 1)$ is the distance that the elevator travels during acceleration and braking at each stage.

3. Time spent on stops (opening/closing doors, passengers entering and exiting):

- The time spent on passenger entry/exit and door opening/closing is usually calculated using formulas based on cabin capacity and the number of passengers.

- This data can be obtained from tables or standard values for specific elevator types.

4. Adjustment by factor 1.1:

Sometimes the overall time calculation is adjusted by a factor of 1.1 to account for various factors such as additional time losses, equipment wear and tear, or additional time for delays between flights.

Let's substitute the data:

$$T = \frac{(2 \cdot H_v + h \cdot (N_v + 1))}{V} + \frac{1}{1} \cdot \Sigma T$$

$$= \frac{(2 \cdot 35.84 + 2 \cdot (5.5 + 1))}{1.00} + 1.1 \cdot 96$$

$$T = \frac{(71.68 + 2 \cdot 6.5)}{1.00} + 1.1 \cdot 96$$

$$T = \frac{(71.68 + 13)}{1.00} + 105.6$$

$$T = \frac{84.68}{1.00} + 105.6 = 84.68 + 105.6 = 190.28 \approx 190 \text{ s}$$

The elevator's round trip time is 190 seconds..

Let's look at the key aspects, thus:

- 1. Occupancy of one floor:**
- The standard occupancy rate is 19 people per floor, which is the standard indicator for calculating passenger flow.
- 3. Service comfort level:**
- With the interval of elevator movement $t_i = 100 \text{ s}$ (satisfactory level), the calculated time of the elevator round trip $T = 190 \text{ s}$ corresponds to a good level of comfort with two elevators
- 5. Load capacity and speed of elevators:**

- Each lift is designed for a load capacity of 400 kg (5 people).
- The elevator speed is 1 m/s, which corresponds to standard values for mid-rise residential buildings (up to 17 floors).

6. Number of elevators:

Taking into account the calculated values (round trip time, probable number of passengers, number of stops), two elevators can handle the load quite well.

For a residential building with 17 floors, a standard occupancy of 19 people per floor, and an elevator load capacity of 400 kg (at a speed of 1 m/s), two elevators are sufficient to provide a comfortable level of passenger service.

Short circuits that occur during the operation of electrical systems can lead to serious consequences, such as equipment damage, power supply disruption and hazardous situations. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a detailed analysis of electrical networks and install protective devices that will ensure reliable operation of the systems.

Table 3 shows the active resistances of the contact connections of cables.

TABLE 3. ACTIVE RESISTANCES OF ALUMINUM CABLES

Cross-section of aluminum cable, mm ²	16	25	35	50	70	95	120	150	240
Resistances mOm	0.085	0.064	0.056	0.043	0.029	0.027	0.024	0.021	0.012

TABLE 4. RESISTANCES OF COILS AND CONTACTS OF CIRCUIT BREAKERS

Nom. Sw. Current, A	50	70	100	140	200	400	600	1000	1600	2500	4000
r_{KB}	7	3.5	2.15	1.3	1.1	0.65	0.41	0.25	0.14	0.13	0.1
x_{KB}	4.5	2	1.2	0.7	0.5	0.16	0.13	0.1	0.08	0.07	0.05

We will determine the resistance of the system as follows:

$$x_c = \frac{U_{\text{aver.nv}}^2}{\sqrt{3} \cdot I_{\text{off.nom}} \cdot U_{\text{cp.BH}}} = \frac{6000}{34.64 \cdot 400} = 0.7698004$$

In this way we can determine the resistance of the transformer.

TABLE 5. CALCULATED DATA FOR THE TRANSFORMER

1	$r_T = \frac{P_{k.nom} \cdot U_{nn.nom}^2}{S_{m.HOM}^2} \cdot 10^2$	3.063744
2	$x_T = \sqrt{u_k^2 - \left[\frac{100 \cdot P_{k.HOM}}{S_{T.HOM}} \right]^2} \cdot \frac{U_{nn.nom}^2}{S_{T.nom}} \cdot 10^2$	13.628118
3	$U_{nn.nom}$ kV	0.4
4	$P_{k.nom}$ kW	7.6
5	U_k , %	5.5
6	$S_{T.nom}$ kVA	630

The TMG-630/6/0.4 transformer was used for the calculation.

A transformer substation is a structure for placing process equipment. Access to process equipment is provided through process openings and by removing and opening protective

panels. The presence of people and access of people inside the spaces of a transformer substation is not provided for and is not possible.

Based on the above, we can calculate the short circuit currents.

TABLE 6. EXAMPLES OF CALCULATING SHORT-CIRCUIT CURRENTS FOR DIFFERENT NETWORK POINTS

Short circuit point	Calculation of short-circuit currents	
	$I_{no}^{(3)} = \frac{U_{cp.HOM}}{\sqrt{3} \cdot \sqrt{r_{1\Sigma}^2 + x_{1\Sigma}^2}}$	$I_{no}^{(1)} = \frac{\sqrt{3} \cdot U_{cp.HOM}}{\sqrt{(2r_{1\Sigma} + r_{0\Sigma})^2 + (2x_{1\Sigma} + x_{0\Sigma})^2}}$
Main switchboard	6.17	3300
Boiler room	2.97	2375
Switchboard OLS	4.04	2185
Group OL-1	0.21	185
Group OL-2	0.21	185
Group OL-3	0.10	95

Also, the resistances of the network elements are required, shown in Table 7.

TABLE 7. RESISTANCES OF NETWORK ELEMENTS

Cable line/busbar						
Brand	Section	Length L, m	r_{1kl}, mOm	r_{0kl}, mOm	x_{1kl}, mOm	x_{0kl}, mOm
AVBBShvng-LS	240	150	24	115.5	4.8	40.9
AVBBShvng-LS	16	25	60	109.8	2.1	39
VVGng-LS	4	10	22.69	87.1	0.94	19.7
AVBBShvng-LS	4	110	1057	1288	10.78	232
AVBBShvng-LS	4	110	1057	1288	10.78	232
AVBBShvng-LS	4	225	2162	2635	22.05	475

CONTINUATION OF TABLE 7

Switch. Automatic.		Contact connections		Total resistances			
Brand	r_{as}, mOm	x_{as}, mOm	r_k, mOm	r_{1y}, mOm	r_{0y}, mOm	x_{1y}, mOm	x_{0y}, mOm
AVBBShvng-LS	0.41	0.13	0.048	32.06	123.6	19.33	55.4
AVBBShvng-LS	7	4.5	0.17	74.77	124.5	21	57.85
VVGng-LS	7	4.5	0.17	52.17	189.8	23.68	71.28
AVBBShvng-LS	7	4.5	0.17	1116	1485	28.96	307.9
AVBBShvng-LS	7	4.5	0.17	1116	1485	38.96	307.9
AVBBShvng-LS	7	4.5	0.17	2222	2832	50.23	550.5

To ensure safety in case of fire, one of the elevators in the building must be equipped with a system that provides transportation of fire brigades. In the mode of operation of the elevator intended for firefighters:

Fig. 1. Automation diagram of the supply unit P-2

Direct intercom: is established between the control center, the elevator cabin and the main landing floor for rapid response and coordination of actions.

The automated control system of dispatching (ACDS) is designed to ensure effective monitoring, safety and voice

communication in the elevator industry of a residential complex. It includes several key components and functions to ensure the reliability of elevators and rapid response in emergency situations.

Fig. 2. Elevator control diagram N°1

1. Elevator Safety Monitoring

The ASUD system provides monitoring of the following important signals to improve the safety of elevator operation:

- Triggering of electrical safety circuits: monitoring of electrical circuits responsible for the safety of the elevator, such as emergency braking circuits, overload protection circuits, etc.
- Unauthorized opening of shaft doors: alarm in case of an attempt to open the elevator shaft doors without permission.
- Opening of the door (cover) of the elevator control device without a machine room: alarm in case of unauthorized access to the elevator control panel, if it is located in dangerous or prohibited areas.

2. Voice communication with the dispatcher

To ensure prompt communication with the dispatcher, as well as for communication in emergency situations, the following communication channels are provided:

- Intercom equipment supplied with lifts: standard intercoms built into the lift car.
- Machine room intercom: equipment for communication with the lift equipment and technical personnel located in the machine room.
- Main landing floor intercom: enables the dispatcher or lift user to quickly communicate with the lift car.
- Roof intercom (if required): used for emergency communication in the event of a lift being blocked in the shaft.
- Pit intercom: in the event of an emergency on the lower floor, the lift pit, this communication will provide control and assistance.

To implement all functions of monitoring and control of elevators, as well as to organize effective voice communication in the elevator system of the residential complex, the ASUD "OB" system is used. This allows:

- Monitor the status of elevators in real time.
- Communicate with elevator users and the dispatcher in case of an emergency.
- Ensure uninterrupted and safe operation of the elevator system.

The ASUD system significantly increases the safety of elevator operation, improves the efficiency of response to emergency situations and guarantees effective voice communication between the dispatcher and users, including fire departments.

The selection of optimal design solutions was made on the basis of:

- rational structural design of the building;
- economic comparative analysis of the cost of various structural designs;
- use of materials that have adequate resistance (frost resistance, moisture resistance, bioresistance, corrosion resistance, resistance to temperature effects, including cyclic ones, to other destructive effects of the environment), providing, if necessary, special protection of structural elements in order to ensure durability and standard service life of the building.

The designed residential building is equipped with the following types of lighting: working and emergency (backup and evacuation), as well as repair.

The voltage of the general lighting network is 380/220V, the voltage on the lamps is 220V, the voltage of the repair lighting is 36V. Centralized lighting control is not provided. Control of the working lighting of public areas (stairwells, elevator halls, corridors) is carried out automatically using motion sensors.

To calculate the annual consumption of electrical energy for common house needs (using the example of an apartment building with elevators), you can use the formula:

$$E_{г/эл} = \sum (P_{calc} \cdot k_{day} \cdot k_{year} \cdot \Delta t_i) \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ MWh.}$$

where:

• P_{calc} — estimated capacity of consumers taking into account the demand coefficient (kW); $P_{calc} = 120 \text{ kW}$ (total capacity of equipment of elevators, pumps and other devices).

• $k_{day} = 0.500$ — energy efficiency (proportion of hours of operation per day);

• $k_{year} = 1.000$ — energy efficiency (percentage of days of operation per year);

• Δt_i — operating time of the i -th consumer per year, calculated using the formula:

$$\Delta t_i = k_{day} \cdot k_{year} \cdot 8760 = 0.500 \cdot 1.000 \cdot 8760 = 4380 \text{ hour/year}$$

where 8760 is the total number of hours in a year;

Annual electricity consumption:

$$E_{y/el} = P_{calc} \cdot \Delta t_i \cdot 10^{-3} = 120 \cdot 4380 \cdot 10^{-3} = 526 \text{ mWh/year}$$

Specific energy consumption:

$$E_{sp} = \frac{E_{y/el}}{\text{square}} = \frac{526}{10171,96} = 0.05 \text{ mWh/year/m}^2$$

Basic level of specific annual electricity consumption for common house needs (apartment buildings with elevators): 10,0 kWh/m

LABOR PROTECTION AND SAFE OPERATION MEASURES

In order to protect service personnel from electric shock, all metal non-current-carrying parts of the ASUD equipment that are not normally energized but may become energized as a result of insulation breakdown on the housing must be grounded.

The resistance of the grounding device used for grounding electrical equipment must be no more than 0.5 Ohm.

There should be no disconnecting devices or fuses in the grounding conductor circuit. The connection of grounding to the equipment parts should be performed by welding or bolted connection, in accordance with the Electrical Installation Code.

Environmental protection

The equipment and devices used to create the ASUD do not create environmental pollution.

CONCLUSION

As part of the feasibility study for the calculations of elevators and short circuits in a residential complex, a comprehensive analysis was conducted, including the calculation of the operating parameters of elevator equipment, as well as modeling of electrical networks to assess the safety and efficiency of their operation.

Key findings:

1. Calculations of elevator equipment:

• Time expenditures for key stages of elevator operation (acceleration, braking, opening and closing doors) were determined, which made it possible to calculate the total duration of the operating cycle.

• An assessment of the annual energy consumption of elevators and related equipment was performed, ensuring the reliability and energy efficiency of the elevator system. It was established that the specific annual energy consumption complies with regulatory requirements.

2. Short circuit analysis:

• Calculation of short-circuit currents at key points of the residential complex's electrical network, such as the main distribution board (MDB), boiler room, and floor distribution boards, was performed. This allowed us to assess the safety of the electrical infrastructure and identify its critical parameters.

• Active and reactive resistances of cable lines, circuit breakers, and transformers were determined. The data obtained allowed us to refine the electrical network parameters and select optimal protective devices.

3. Monitoring and security system:

- A concept for an elevator monitoring system using an automated dispatch control system has been developed, which ensures timely response to emergency situations and operational safety.

- Voice communication elements and fire brigade transportation functions have been included to provide additional levels of safety.

Recommendations:

1. Ensure the implementation of the ASUD "OB" system for centralized monitoring of the condition of elevator equipment and electrical infrastructure.

2. Install protective devices designed for maximum short-circuit currents to eliminate overloads and minimize the risk of emergency situations.

3. Regularly conduct energy audits and checks of elevator equipment to improve its reliability and reduce energy costs.

Conclusion:

The calculations performed confirmed that the proposed technical solutions ensure safety, energy efficiency and reliability of the electrical infrastructure and elevator equipment of the residential complex. The use of modern monitoring and control systems will optimize operating costs and increase the comfort of residents.

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